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STATE CENTRAL LIBRARY MUMBAI AND MARATHI PUBLICATIONS: AN ANALYSIS

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Abstract:

The growth of the collection of Marathi books at State central library Mumbai was due to the legal deposit system. The printed and non print materials preserve the cultural heritage. For preserving the Marathi publication, State central library is playing a vital role. The State Central library is act as a depository center for PR act and DB act. The trends of Marathi publication in the year 2012 is discussed in this paper.

1. Introduction:

The cultural heritage of India has been reflected from the written materials in various forms. India is a multilingual with multiscript country, to organize all the material published in various parts of India and preserved them is not an easy task. Central Reference Library and National Library, Kolkata has taken the huge task of the preparation of National bibliography of all these 14 major languages since 1954 and they published Indian National Bibliography (INB) regularly. Legal deposit acts play an important role for the bibliographic control of print materials. Under this legal act, the books has been received at National Library Kolkata as well as other three designated libraries viz. Delhi Public Library, Connemara Public Library and State Central library, Mumbai. According to Gorman (2004), for Universal bibliographic control every country has to be prepared their bibliography and make it available throughout the world. We can continue this statement as each States of India has to be prepared their bibliographies for the betterment of National Bibliography.

For Maharashtra state, State central library, Mumbai is one of the designated library received the books under Delivery of Books 1954, and Press and Registration Act, 1867. The contribution towards the bibliographic control on Marathi books should be initiated by State Central Library, Mumbai. This paper is mainly focused on the Marathi books received under PR Act.

2. State Central Library (SCL), Mumbai:

The State Central Library (SCL) is controlled by Directorate of Libraries, Govt. of Maharashtra. It was established on the recommendation of Fyzee committee. Earlier the function of state central library was assigned to Asiatic society Bombay in 1947. Later on the Directorate of libraries was set up on 2nd May 1968 and State Central library was established at Directorate office. This library is expected to perform the bibliographic functions as acquisition, maintenance and preservation of books and periodicals received under the PR Act and DB Act. Compile and published the bibliographies in the state for the use of public, scholars and research workers.

2.1 Marathi Publications:

Marathi is one of the ancient and richest languages of India with a great literary tradition. As per Pathare (2013) the earliest available literary work in Marathi is almost 2000 years old. The printing of Marathi publications was introduced by Jesuit Missionaries. The first proper printed book in Marathi was published in 1805 by Dr. William Carey under the title 'A Grammar of Marahatta Language. Later on the publications were developed all over the Maharashtra. Today, in terms of rank, almost 110 million people speak Marathi in almost 72 countries, and it stands among the first 15 largest spoken languages in the world. Presently there are more than seven hundred publishers are in Marathi publication industry. The Marathi publication industry produced 2000 books every year.

2.2 The press and Registration of Book Act 1867:

The British Government has enacted this law in 1867. The act has been amended with 'Thirteen Amendments between 1890 and 1960. However, the major provisions remained unchanged compelling the delivery of copies of each book and each newspaper for the scrutiny of state authorities.

3. Objectives of the study:

The present paper is to study the inclusion of Marathi titles at State Central Library under the PR act. Following are the some objectives set for the present study.

We have following the broad objectives of this study are as follows;

- To know the current status of Marathi titles at State Central Library.
- To study the inclusion of Marathi titles in PR Act at SCL.
- To examine the relevant feature of Marathi titles at SCL

4. Significance of the Study:

The study is useful to know the importance of legal deposit act for preserving the Marathi publication. This material will helpful for the future generation to know the cultural heritage of Maharashtra. It is also important to aware the press and registration act and role of printers to preserve the materials at SCL. The preparation of bibliography, the standardization and the bibliographic details are very much important to understand before starting the digitization of bibliographic sources.

5. Scope and Limitation of the Study:

Our aim is to study the Marathi publication in Maharashtra from an authentic source i.e. State central library, Mumbai. The books received under the PR Act at SCL during calendar year of 2012 are selected for the study.

6. Review of Related Literature:

There are only few research has been done on the bibliographic control of Marathi publications. Sharma (1981) has completed the dissertation for the degree of Master of library science at university of Poona, on bibliographic control of Marathi publications: a critical survey. She has critically examine and a systematic evaluation of all types of bibliographical tools. The actual status of the Marathi Resources has not been examined by any research. Paul (2008) had deals with the role of legal deposit law i.e. PR act, 1867 and its resultant current bibliographies in bibliographic control of Bengali publications. Mahajan (2003) had attempted to describe the efforts made by Shankar Ganesh Date and other organizations toward the bibliographic control of Marathi publications. According to Deshpande (1997), the literary history project in Marathi has remained unmindful of the polarities, internal contradictions and tensions which seem to have dominated both the literary discourse and literary production in Marathi since the 13th century. Pathare(2013) had described the status of Marathi language, its historical perspectives for the purpose of classical language in India.

7. Research Methodology:

The Descriptive methodology is used for the present study. This method is used to know the accurate way of the participation in the sources. The comprehensive and systematic content of Marathi titles at the sources has been analyzed. The publications of Marathi titles during the year 2012 have been selected. The interpretation of the data has been presented in the tabular form.

8. Data Analysis:

The present data has been selected from the Accession Register of Press and Registration Act, from State Central Library, Mumbai. The following analysis is carried out from the data available during the year 2012. The data was available in Marathi language, which can be transcribed to English. Then the analysis has been carried out by with the help of Microsoft Excel software.

8.1 Title Received at SCL

The titles received under the PR Act at State Central Library Mumbai in the calendar year of 2012 were 1437. These titles were in English, Marathi and Hindi languages. We have selected only Marathi titles for the further analysis.

Table 1: Title received at SCL under PR Act

Language	No. of Title	Percentage
Marathi	1214	84.48
English	174	12.11
Hindi	49	03.41

Total	1437	100.00
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The above table shows that Marathi is the prominent language received at SCL under the PR act. Out of total 84.48% titles was received in Marathi language, followed by English and Hindi language.

8.2 Authors and their Publications:

The Marathi authors have been gradually more increasing in the Marathi publication industry. The trends of author with their publication have been analyzed.

Table 2 Top Authors

Sr. no.	Name of Authors	Total Publication
1	Madgulkar Vyankatesh	22
2	Davane Pravin	20
3	Bhave H A	19
4	Baradkar P N	18
5	Bhivgade Dnyaneshwar	13
6	Joshi Yogesh	13
	Sane Guruji	12
7	Velankar Vandana	12
8	Bujrwa Polet	10
9	Jadhav Tukaram	10
10	Joshi Mahadevshashtri	10

The above table shows that top authors whose publication has been received in the year 2012 at SCL. Madgulkar Vyankatesh had published maximum (22) publications during the year 2012, followed by Davane Pravin, Bhave and Baradkar with titles 20, 19 and 18 respectively. In the top ten lists two women authors are also seen. Such authors work has become inspiration to the new authors in the Marathi publication industry.

8.3 Place of Publication

Place is more important in the publication industry. It reflects the publication trends in the various areas.

Table 3 : Place of Publication

Sr. no.	Places	No. of Books	Percentage
1	Pune	628	51.73
2	Mumbai	305	25.12
3	Thane	52	4.28
4	Nagpur	50	4.12
5	Kolhapur	47	3.87
6	Aurangabad	33	2.72
7	Parbhani	24	1.98

8	Rest of Maharashtra	61	5.02
9	Other states	14	1.15
	Total	1214	100

The above table indicated that the half of the publication were in the pune city. The Mumbai is on the second step where 25% books have been published. The Thane, Nagpur, Kolhapur are in the range of 4%. The publication is also seen in the other parts of the India, where 1.15% books have been published during the period.

The next table indicated the top publishers.

Table 4 Top Publishers

Sr. no.	Type of publisher	No. of Books
1	Mehta Publishing House	115
2	Gandharv ved prakashan	66
3	Navchaitanya Prakashan	52
4	Snehavardhan Prakashan	51
5	Rajhans Prakashan	44
6	Manorama Prakashan	40

The Mehta publishing house has been published total 115 books in the year 2012. It become the first in all publication followed by Gandharv published 66 books, Navchaitanya published 51 books, followed by Rajhans and Manorama. Maximum publishers are based on Pune city.

8.4 Subjects coverage:

Table 5 Subject covered

Sr. no.	Subjects	No. of Books	Percentage
1	Literature	588	48.43
2	Agriculture	8	0.66
3	Arts and Culture	40	3.29
4	History Geography	103	8.48
5	Social Science	391	32.21
6	Science	73	6.01
7	Miscellaneous	11	0.91
	Total	1214	100

The above table indicated that the Literature has been a major part of any language. Total 48.43% titles are related to Marathi Literature and remaining are from Social Science, Agriculture, Arts, History and Science subjects. The new subjects were also seen while doing the study, this indicate that the Marathi publication are goes beyond the literature.

The other observations are as follows;

It is also found that 687(56.59%) authors have published their single book in the year 2012, the 155 authors have been published more than one book, and they published total 527(43.41%) book during the period. The growth is indicated that the authors are coming

forward with more publications. Only 77 titles has been published on collaborative work, while other has published their have published their work as a solo author.

The Repeated title in the year 2012 was 45. This repetition was seen because the titles have not been properly mentioned their bibliographic details at the accession register.

The type of books was received during the year 2012 was classified as, there were total 77 translated book has been received, 20 edited books and 3 compiled book and remaining 1114 books were regular books received.

The edition wise analysis shows that the 1111 (91.52%) titles has published the first edition, while 41 book with 2nd edition and 25 with 3rd edition. It is found that there is a book whose 29th edition was published during the study.

The maximum (46.87%) books have been published in the year 2011 which have been included at SCL in 2012. The 37.49% books published in 2012 and included the same year. The oldest book was published in 1962 and included in 2012.

The analysis shows that there were 1154 (95%) publishers were come under the category of Commercial publishers. Only 25 (2%) publishers where Institutions and 12(1%) as personal publisher and 23(1.89%) are the authors, who published themselves.

The top publishers are given below

9. Conclusion:

The legal deposit law is very much important for the preservation of Marathi publication. The PR act in Maharashtra state working very properly and printers are depositing their printed books at SCL. The growth of Marathi publication is increasing rapidly at SCL. The commercial publishers are contributed toward the Marathi publication industry. It is suggested that the SCL should be published the annual list of books in digitized format.

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